

GAṆEŚA IN DURGĀ'S ARMS: Examining the Mytho-Numismatic Context of a Unique Coin of Bengal

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Abstract

Indian Numismatics is known for myriad of uncanny and unique ways in which divinities and deity-figures find manifestation on the medium of coinage. In many cases, a preliminary perusal of the coin is sufficient to comprehend the contextual contours behind its production and figurative delineation, for some simplicity becomes illusive. One such coin hails from Samatāṭa, Bengal, and depicts an infant Gaṇeśa in arms of Goddess Durgā. Even though the coin stands as an artistic and mytho-culturally significant innovation, it still awaits a standard scholastic treatment. Here, we shall attempt to fill this lacuna by subjecting the coin to a Mytho-Numismatic examination. It is believed that such an exercise would yield rich dividends in not just unveiling the context of this specific coin, but would further throw welcoming light on other topics of associative significance.

Keywords: Samatāṭa, Bengal coins, Durgā, Gaṇeśa, Post-Gupta Numismatics.

Introduction

Coins are one of the most valuable sources of History, for they are remnants of a distant time, possessing their original shape and form. Unlike literary sources, which invariably undergo

redaction, have their core material split into recensions, face multiple interpolations and therefore become distorted from their initial structuration, Archaeological sources enjoy longevity and when studied cautiously, could be comprehended as possessors of historical information that defies significance. Coins have a certain quotient of utilization associated with themselves, since they carry *impressions of the past*, for e.g. metallurgical mastery, condition of economy, circulation-pattern, data about economic behaviour of temporally distant populace, and more importantly, mytho-cultural practices of the times.

Gods and goddesses find frequent appearance and appeal on ancient Indian coins. Getting surprised or amazed by their intimate linkage with monetary media of *ancien regime* can be sufficiently labelled as an anachronistic trait, for Kings and kingdoms more often than not depended upon and actively deployed deity-figures in ‘secular’ matters of governance and economy. Such divinities often acted on coins in the capacity of a promissory agent (Tarn, 1951: 24), or legitimized the authority of issue and control of the reigning monarch (Altekar, 1957: 11).

The presence of particular divinities reveals multiple layers of the past, such as prevalent iconographical conventions, cultural-complex, ritual-order, royal cultic practices, sectarian dynamics, and community engagement with religious milieu. To understand the denotative idea of a specific deity-figure, scholars rely on mythological narratives, sacred textual materials, chronologically linked archaeo-cultural remains, and sometimes, even on prevalent contemporary customs or traditional practices.

The coin under inspection herein has much potential in this regard, but had been subjected to minimal scholarly analysis. In this view, some credit should be given to B.N. Mukherjee (1993: 28), the doyen of numismatic studies in Bengal, who illustrated and described this coin in detail. However, he limited his analytical venture upto the task of assigning a definitive mode of recognition to the authority behind the issuance of this coin-type. However, in our opinion, this coin still has much untapped historical potential and promise, and thence could be rightly used

beyond political history, to gauge developments in mytho-cultural and numismatic domains of action.

In this paper, we shall attempt to perform such an endeavour, an enterprise that requires working comprehension of myriad related to, and intimately integrated with the contextual structuration of this particular coin. Hence, delineation of methodology becomes a sine qua non. Our study herein shall proceed here in due accordance with the following steps-

1. *Firstly*, we shall discuss the genesis of Durgā and Gaṇeśa in a non-Vedic socio-cultural milieu, as has been proposed by several veteran scholars. It is our belief that the function of this coin co-relates strongly with harvest and vegetative function, as shall be highlighted in due course.
2. *Secondly*, we shall trace the mytho-cultural trajectory of development of the mytho-numismatic position of both Durgā and Gaṇeśa in the Gupta realm. This would provision afore us much data of use before we enter the Early Medieval Period for our coin.
3. *Thirdly*, an analytical survey would illustrate the contextual structuration of the particular coin from numismatic and mytho-cultural perspectives, in order to fully comprehend the purpose and intention behind its issuance in the first place.
4. *Lastly*, a summary of all facts and figurative aspects of our study shall be provided to pay respect to the vital dictum of brevity.

Gleaning Genesis of Durgā and Gaṇeśa

As had been pointed out time and again by many scholars, both Durgā (Kinsley, 1988: 92; Banerjea, 1956: 257) and Gaṇeśa (Brown, 1992: 98; Heras, 1972: 28; Getty, 1936: 54) are connected to harvest and vegetative rites and rituals. While fertility is a common denominator for all divine figures within the Śaivite world (Chakrabarti, 1998: 46), Durgā and Gaṇeśa share a

special with not only the countryside ceremonies, but with the very essence of such feats of propitiation (Majumdar, 2021: 51), as evinced from Purāṇic discourses (Hazra, 1958: 211ff.) and folk legends (Grimes, 2010: 98).

The earliest literary reference of Goddess Durgā, with surety of repose and without an iota of interpolation, lies in the *Devī-māhātmyam*, a part of Mārkaṇḍeya Purāṇa (Hazra, 2025 [1940]: 90). While references to the Goddess with the name Durgā also find somewhat slighting mentions in the *Gāyatrī* section of *Taittreya Āraṇyaka* [unanimously assigned to 10th Century CE (Kinsley, 1988: 135)], in the Virāṭa Parvam of the *Mahābhāratam* (ch. 25-38), where her description closely befits that of Vindhyavāsīnī, albeit enmeshed with complex and confounding narratives (Mazumdar, 1906: 358). After the poetically supreme and narratively furious description of Devī-māhātmyam, a standard template was structured for the deity-figure, which finds reiteration in later textual references (Kinsley, 1988: 140).

The concept of 'Durgā' challenges previous Mythological narratives, where Śaivite Mother-Goddess was envisioned as a Consort Goddess, closely and intimately connected with the narratives and functions of her husband. But, Durgā inverts this narrational scheme in more than one way, such as-

1. She is shown adept in the practice and utilization of weapons and military tactics, which are often considered as masculine domains.
2. She is not dependent on any God, and neither supports her male-half in any way. Rather, she draws energies from various gods, and creates innumerable horrendous forces of her own to combat Asura menace.
3. She challenges patriarchal thinking in her combative replied to the playful and dismissive offers of marriage, furthered to her time and again by her nemesis, chiefly Mahiṣāsura.

4. Her character challenges Śāstras, which enjoin that women, unprotected by men, are always helpless, and require masculine protection. Her stories depict her unbending to ‘male gaze’, and fiercely independent.

Rahman (1965: 66) postulated that goddess Durgā had emerged from the innumerable village deities Grāma Devatā worshipped through the length and breadth of India. The proximity and continuity of the deity’s presence often and obviously multiplied the degree of intimacy between the revered and revering (Pattanaik, 2000: 86). The sprinkling of vermilion of the aniconic stone representative of the deity was a mutated symbolic assertion of its textually verified and observationally sanctified precursor- blood. As Pattanaik (2016: 29) postulated, the figurative inclusions and accruements in the static stone-figure of the deity, such as eyes, hands, and vermilion made its presence, preferably and generally on or near the peripheral demarcations of the village, more impressive and lively, and gave the goddess an animative power, that further increased the trust of the common masses upon the divine. With the Devī-māhātmyam model, many local goddesses were felicitously linked with Durgā. Another cause of the rapid spread of popularity of Durgā cult amongst Śākta worshippers was her tribal roots.

Mazumdar (1906: 362) was the first scholar to highlight the tribal origins of Durgā. His study of Osna-Kumārī festival of indigenous people of Sambalpur led him to derive derivative formulations from a core, un-orthodox tribal sacred concept (*ibid*, 1906: 362-65), which he later contrasted with the much ambiguous and contorted narration of Virāṭa Parvam of Mahābhāratam; he essentially contended that the scribes and compilers of Mahābhāratam had garnered this sacred imagery from the tribal orbits of existence, adjunct to Āryandom, a fact also corroborated in later linguistic researches related to the Great War (Mehendale, 2002). This section of the Epic described the Mother Goddess (also of victory) as- “Ravishing with blood, brandishing swords of great destruction.... She lives in the Vindhya, a being of four arms, dark as darkness manifest, covered by foliated leaves, decorated with blood, she roams hitherto upon her vicious lions with

ferocity unseen....a daughter of Nanda and Yaśodā, she runs with the cowherds (Mazumdar, 1906: 364). While her linkage to Nanda and Yaśodā connects her quite potently with the Ābhīra-clan, regarded as foreigners in Ancient literature (Suryavanshi, 1962: 21-26), the gradual intermingling of the recent arrivals, together with their conflation with native cowherds, and their second migration southwards (Suryavanshi, 1962 15) positions them well in the Vindhyan region, where the nearby Deogarh Daśāvatāra Temple, where the couple are shown in foreign, rather Scythian garbs (Agrawala, 1965: 58). The configuration of Durgā in this section is generally attested to 5th-6th century CE, a period till when the Ābhīra-clan had underwent poignant and piquant Indianization (Suryavanshi, 1962: 34). Moreover, later texts categorically illustrate mass migrations from Vindhyas towards Bengal (*Gauḍavāho* of Vākpatirāja, see Bhowmik, 2004: 50ff.) between c. 6th-7th Century CE (Mishra, 1971: 266). It is possible that the popularity of Durgā has an inaugural connection with such events and movements.

The cult of Goddess Durgā both transformed into or rather coalesced other localized goddess cults (Sircar, 1948: 12). It is believed that with the advent of pastoral nomadism, once predominant Mother-goddess cults became obscure. But, with the resurgence of reverence of Durgā, the suppressed cultic supremacy of Mother-goddess again experienced a return to form, with the establishment of Śākta sect, given conditional obeisance and patronage by aspiring monarchs with regional visions and tribal affiliations. Her gender-role too shifted, from being a novice consort to a seasoned warrior, and her worshippers too asked for blessings in martial, and not household or marital affairs. This was not to remain stable. The mid-phase of Early Medieval Period, during c. 9th-11th Century CE saw a revolutionary rise of Śaivism, which even began to encapsulate Durgā, by explaining her mythological form as a deviant of Pārvatī and Umā. Her domestication process (specifically in c. 7th Century CE Bengal) was accomplished by making changes in her character (less belligerent, playful marital status), removal of certain epithets (especially those highlighting her unfavorable stance to marriage), iconographical innovation (addition of drapery, household items in added arms, ostentation), and occasions of worship

(autumnal, harvest festivals). Her absolute absorption within Sanskritic tradition left space for newer local Mother-Goddesses to occupy her position. In context of Early Medieval Bengal, Sircar (2004: 12) further notes-

It speaks of the crafty ingenuity of the local episcopacy that, by the simple device of eliminating the great Hindu triad from later Durgā -stelas, they ensured not only that the goddess's hegemonic symbols were removed, but also that leaving her alone with just her two sons would gradually lead to the replacement of her war-like prowess with expected maternal 'softness'.

Now, regarding the origination of Gaṇeśa- while Non-Vedic essentially do not translate implicitly or even surreptitiously into tribal, Dravidian or other heterodox origins (Courtright, 1991), it mostly illustrates the penetration of cults from a socio-cultural locus located outside the Vedic sacred-complex. In this vein, Krishan (1981: 55) highlights some reasonable facets of the life and personality of Gaṇeśa, which taint him in Non-Vedic colors. Datta (1959: 154) also posited the relatively earlier severance of Gaṇeśa from the Vedic World in these words- "When the previously diabolical deity [re-]entered the Vedic World, his cognizance was purported by assigning him not a human body, shape or form, but that of a creature not controlled, feared or feigned by the Vedic populace. This singularly highlights the downward placement given to a God figure, who was only conditionally acceptable." Krishan (1981: 58) highlighted that his association inauspicious phenomena and places Gaṇeśa in a category not visited by the Vedic deities; while some of them had some ulterior grey shades to their characters, no deity-figure was entrenched in affiliations with the dark and grim.

It was earlier emphasized by Sir R.G. Bhandarkar (1913: 49-58) that Gaṇeśa was a relatively late entrant into the Vedic pantheon, who found complete reiteration and absolute veneration only during the Purāṇic epoch. Gupte emphatically asserted that the hymns to Gaṇeśa in Brāhmaṇa texts point toward his affinity with agricultural growth and fecundity. He envisaged a creatively surcharges farmer, who in the dangling corn-sheaf, pointed snake-hood and

impositional movement saw a deity worthy of propitiation for apotropaic reasons, a function which also brings the rat to bear an equation with his master. However, Michael (1983: 93) rightly rejected this conjecture outright, and contended that the illusionary metaphysical ensemble of iconographical features can only be appropriately considered as integrated of a clear and categorical causative linkage is established, regarding the formative and adoptive phases of the symbolic feat. Furthermore, the symbol must have a contextual allusion with its point or place of origination, another argumentative assault on this bold conjecture, since earliest sculptures depicting an elephant-headed deity-figure have been found in Kuṣāṇa-era stratum of archaeological assemblage at Mathurā. As Bhandarkar (1913: 56) rightly posited, Gaṇeśa was connected with agricultural practices only after acquiring legitimacy in Brāhmaṇic circles, after which the inversion of his initial mythical feats was given special sanctity, chiefly in his iconographical relation with Goddess of plentitude- Lakṣmī, whose existent symbolic associations with Gajas was a well recognized symbol of both assured abundance and bounteous prosperity. Therein lies the Nexus of entrance of Gaṇeśa in rituals of harvest.

However, an exception exists. It has been established here earlier that cult of Gaṇeśa evolved from unorthodox roots. An example of significance can be cited here. The Buddhist text, *Sūta Nipāta* (Davids, 1903: 162) describes an elephant cult, wherein unruly 'evil' elephants were offered worship by locals (called *Prāchya*- Easterners, including Bihar and Bengal) in order to keep them away from trampling crops or ruining harvest. It is possible that with the emergence of Gaṇeśa as an important deity-figure in Brāhmaṇical ritual-order, and later transposition of Brāhmaṇic belief-system across the Gupta Empire (c. 320-550 CE), caused the conception of an elephant god to occur differently in every region, and Gaṇeśa was surreptitiously linked with the elephant cult mentioned in *Sutta Nipāta*. Additionally, it could have been a deliberate stratagem of Brāhmaṇic communities or Purāṇic redactors to make Purāṇic Hinduism as encompassing and enveloping as was possible (Sinha, 2022: 465). Through this, localized cults or tribal deity-figures were effectually integrated with mainstream ritual-order.

Glimpses of Durgā and Gaṇeśa from the Gupta Age:

In this section, we shall highlight the numismatic depiction of both Durgā and Gaṇeśa in order to have a glimpse of their mytho-numismatic positions. This endeavor shall serve us profitably in the next section, where we will analyze our coin of imperative consideration.

Fig. 01: Chandragupta-Kumāradevī type of coin, featuring (possibly) Goddess Durgā on reverse (Courtesy- The British Museum, 1894, 0506. 147).

The appearance of Durgā on Gupta Coins has been a contentious issue. However, since our primary contention here differs from it, we shall lay out the bare details. Chandragupta-Kumāradevī gold-coin depicts a Goddess sitting atop a lion, who is considered as either Lakṣmī (Altekar, 1957: 14; Srinivasan, 2005: 132; Raven, 1994: 35) or Durgā (Mukherjee, 1993: 29; Ghose, 2006: 23; Yokochi, 2005: 336). However, this conundrum is easily solvable using a terracotta seal discovered at Rajghat, which shows a Goddess atop a lion with the legend *Durgāh* (Mukherjee, 1993: 21). From this, one fact of significance becomes evident- Durgā was considered as a Royal Goddess, on par with Lakṣmī, and her numismatic figuration was clearly derived from that of Nanā, her somewhat intercultural equivalent in Kuṣāṇa pantheon (Shrava, 1985: 94). This presents much data of relevance to us, since Nanā was considered as the Goddess of Natural plenitude and abundance, as learnt from Rabatak Inscription (Sims-Williams, 2008), an

observation the Guptas were cognizant of, due to the extensive statuary and epigraphical registers that record this assertion (Ghose, 2006: 60). This proves at length that before the completion of Gupta Age, Durgā had assumed a form that allows us to reach our item of interest.

The numismatic iteration of Gaṇeśa naturally brings several other considerations, chiefly the numismatic presence of Elephants. Therefore, before we categorically illustrate the definitive appearance of Gaṇeśa, a preliminary discourse regarding elephantine figures on Gupta coins must be addressed first.

The depiction-style and utilization potential of Elephant as a symbol of Imperial prowess and wealth was closely observed by the Guptas (Raven, 2015: 82), which they had witnessed on the gold coins of Huviṣka with relatively high gold content (3.92 g out of 7.67 g total) in select areas of Western Uttar Pradesh, and Northern Vidisha region, the two localities with budding and burgeoning business communities and highly effective trade centres (Kumar, 2017: 142). However, the first Gupta monarch to rightly place the Elephant on the reverse of his gold coins was Kumāragupta I. Raven (2015: 69) with certitude in affirmation, proclaims, based on mint-idiomatic studies, that the coin possibly stands as a magnificent product of Mint 7 out of the ten mints operating in the regime of Kumāragupta I, based on attributional affiliates, standing posture, pose and physique of the Emperor on obverse. Variety A depicts Kumāragupta I bemusing himself on an elephant back, with the legend Mahendra-gajaha in the right-field of the reverse. Raven discusses the obverse device as- “The king straddles atop the mighty beast, his legs covered by its ears. He lifts a goad in his right hand. An attendant crouches behind, raising the royal umbrella above his Master. A fillet waves down from the umbrella’s shaft. The stylistic affinity with other designs from the group is evident in the king’s curly hairdo, his sharp facial features and the muscularity of his bare torso. The attendant has been given similar features in a slightly coarser fashion. His lank body curves forward, more or less following the edge of the coin. As in the related designs, the circular legend on the obverse has been carved in square akṣaras distributed

along the edge with ample interspacing”. Altekar (1957: 194) considered the device as showing Kumāragupta engaged in sport activity. But, given the legend, it hardly elicits itself as such a venture.

Fig. 02: Elephant-rider Coins of Kumāragupta I (Courtesy- Raven, 2015: fig. 05-6).

On Variety B, variously called or referred to as Elephant-rider lion-slayer type (Altekar, 1957: 195-96), Kumāragupta is shown combatant with a ferocious lion, with which he fights from the back of the Elephant. Raven (2015: 69) posits that possibly both coins come from the same mint, as warranted by the representation of the Emperor on obverse. For the second variety, the legend besides the Gupta Goddess reads *śrīmahendragajaḥ*, which scholars often translate into The Lion-slaying elephant of Kumāragupta (Altekar, 1957: 196). However, Raven (2015: 78) somewhat more accurately captures the essence of the description- “The Lion-killer Elephant Kumāragupta “. Raven’s choice of translation augurs well with the legend on obverse- *kṣataripu-kumāragupto rājatrātā jayati ripūn*, starting from 12 o’ clock. Since the Elephant is depicted killing/crushing the lion, the Protector of State should naturally be Mahendra alias Kumāragupta I. However, it could also be an allusion to the synonymous meaning of Mahendra and Indra, with the Elephant being Airāvata, the mount of the King of Gods. The claim to divinity of the Emperor may have rested on his glorious closure of the Kathiawar Campaign against the Western Kṣatrapas,

a deed closely and implicitly highlighted in obverse legend. Furthermore, the reverse of Variety B shows the Goddess feeding peacock, where the type has been highlighted as a victory token of the valiant King, the occasion permitting the mint-master to draw equivalence between the King and his namesake Lord- Kārttikeya. Hence, the King here is Lord Indra in letter and spirit, a possibility rendered fruitful by the epithet (*Mahendrāditya*) of the Kumāragupta I.

Fig. 03: Sculpture of Gaṇeśa carved on Ramgarh Hills (Courtesy- Berkson, 1978: 212, pl. 03).

Interestingly, this was also the period when Gaṇeśa was gaining ready entry and allowance to become a critical member of the Śaivite pantheon (Dhavalikar, 1990: 5), as proved by his statuary in temples of Bhumra and Udaygiri. The sculptural tradition is a clear continuation of

post-Kuṣāṇa era art, and shows marked regional variation, also made possible by the different surface selected for executing the endeavor at hand. Berkson (1978: 212-217) discovered two depictions of Gaṇeśa, made in high relief, in the Rocky outcrops of Ramgarh Hill, dated to early decades of c. 5th Century CE. Gaṇeśa is depicted as sitting in *Ardha-paryanka* pose, with the trunk turned to left, possibly grasping some sweetmeats arranged in a now desiccated platter (see image below). In a way, it can be confidently attested that by this time, Gaṇeśa had gained the rapport and repute needed to later transform and configure into a major deity-figure with a cult of his own.

Fig. 04: Terracotta Seal featuring Gaṇeśa on obverse and couchant bull with the legend Jāgīśvara on reverse (Courtesy- Dr. Prakash Kothari, Deccan Chronicle 30th of August,

2016, Kothari, 2024: pl. 02).

Although Gaṇeśa in his proper therio-cephalic form was not depicted on coins until the Medieval Period (*cf.* Nāyaka and Marāṭhā coins), he begins to occupy a prominent position into mainstream Hinduism, and by the end of Gupta period (mid of c. 6th Century CE) is also shown on official temple seals. A seal, variously dated from c. 3rd to 7th Century CE depicts a seated Gaṇeśa in *Ardha-paryanka* mudra, with trunk turned left on the front, while the reverse shows couchant bull to left in the upper register, and the legend *Jāgīśvara*. The terracotta seal was located

in Chor Bazar, Mumbai, and therefore its exact provenance hitherto remains unknown. From its Paleography, however, the seal shows developed form of Northern variety of Gupta script (Buehler, 1898: 135), as was practised in North India during c. 7th-8th Century CE (Singh, 1990: 19).

Entering the Early Medieval World of our coin

The case of Gaṇeśa has been sufficiently dealt with in the previous sections. Now, it is pertinent to describe the position of Durgā in Early Medieval Period, which initially saw a strong Śākta resurgent undercurrent, which however swiftly subsided with the advent of Śaivism (Chakravarti, 1998: 273), and created orientational pressures, which effectively moved Durgā (now enmeshed with Pārvatī, consort par excellence) towards heightened domesticity, as glimpsed from texts and traditions of these times (Sircar, 2004: 5).

After the disintegration of Gupta Empire, political landscape witnessed rise of regional kingdoms, centered around a nuclear polity (Kulke, 1993: 196). These emergent States expanded politico-economically through *peasantization* (subjecting earlier independent agrarian populace to control) and *ritualization* (inducing regularity in administrative practices and customs). In this expansionist process, they also attempted to incorporate cultic practices of conquered tribes, people into their own, while keeping native traditions at a slightly elevated level (Sharma, 1983: 56). However, it is to be noticed that their own religious and cultural heritage were tribal, or rather peripheral to Brāhmaṇical ritual praxis. To gain political aggrandizement and legitimation amongst Brāhmaṇa communities, collation of their (chiefly) native (Mother) Goddesses figures with highly standardized Brāhmaṇical pantheon became essential. This requirement met resolution through Purāṇic co-relation, a method that entailed either composition of a novel Purāṇa text, or addition of previously non-existing details in Mythological narrative of the Goddess, as evidenced in the case of Kāmākhyā, a Mother-goddess deity-figure in Ancient Kāmarūpa, who was later adopted in mainstream Hinduism in two ways- a) conflation with Goddess Durgā, possibly to

emphasize valorous traits of the Goddess and her sons, i.e. literally, the King, who officiated in many ceremonies in the capacity of Goddesses' son (Rosati, 2017: 52), and b) independently as a unique and singular Mother Goddess, with sphere of influence particularly delimited to Kāmarūpa, as evidenced in the Kālikāpurāṇa (Hazra, 1958: 262). Thus, as regional identity upsurged to gain a place of recognition in the discourse of politics, regional Goddesses too forayed forward with the patronage of her 'sons' and textual-mythological interpolations performed by colluding Brāhmaṇas.

Now, we shall turn out numismatic attention to the region of Samatāṭa in Bengal, Division D (Mukherjee, 1992: 6), where the demise of the Guptas brought numerous petty powers in deadlock competition with each other for acquiring greater power and piety, along with control over the vast overseas trade occurring and enriching the pockets of elites in both administration and business in Samatāṭa. The attentional particularity associated with exchange mechanisms and modes is reflected in the relatively enhanced degree of gold content in such coins, within which one may include the regime of Śaśāṃka (c. 595-627/28 CE), whose short-lived but consequential rule reinvigorated the trade and travails of mercantile Communities in South-east coastal Bengal. After his death, the region of Samatāṭa probably came under the control of Bhāskara-Varmana of Kāmarūpa (c. 605-650 CE), as a procedural outcome of his premeditated deal with Harṣa of Puṣyabhuti Dynasty, wherein the eastern portion of Śaśāṃka's territorial holdings were to be made political dependencies of the Varmana Dynasty, and rendered free from external intervention, while similar, though somewhat unregarded and made asymmetrically conditional due to the clout and prowess of King Harṣa.

The political situation in Post-Śaśāṃka period was one of turmoil and turbulence, with the triangular contest among three royal parties- Bhadras, Rāṭas and Khadgas, with the first gaining power in Samatāṭa around c. 630-35 CE, probably under the command of an Overlord, getting later ousted by the new aspirants waging wars from Northwest region of Vanga, with the same

political fate befalling the other as afore, as evident from Asrafpur grant of Deva-Khadga of c. 685 CE. Scientific excavations carried out at Mainamati have revealed some coins, with similar fabric, style, metrology and execution, bearing somewhat similar devices on both the sides. They perfectly and strictly follow the evolutionary differentiation that caused Samataṭa to initially gain confidence in the market amidst fervid debasement in adjunct Divisions (especially A), and later becoming a target of the same marauding forces of trade manipulation and numismatic maneuvers. The weightage of coins lies, on an average, in the range of about 62 grains to 92.5 grains, showing a continuity of the economic dislike for Suvarṇa standard of the Gupta times, and persistence of the standard set during the heydays of Śaśāṃka's rule, whose mint functioning in Samataṭa fixed the weight at or around 90 grains. The coin that deserves our scrutiny, however, weights about 5.500 grams [=100.08 grains], a slight deviation which could result from faulty blank-preparation or technological obsolescence (Mukherjee, 1993: 24), with gold content of 67.8 %. A description of the specimen is as follows-

Fig. 05: Our Coin of chief consideration (Last copy available in public domain (Courtesy-

The Indian Museum, Kolkata, Reg. No. 18098, Mukherjee, 1993: pl. 3, fig.05).

Obv: A royal figure within dotted borders, standing with head to the right, wearing customary royal garbs, holding an elongated, in-curved bow in left-hand, right-hand outstretched to side, an arrow with head pointing downwards held along with the bow, standard with Bull-symbol, kept on a stand immersed in a Kumbha. The legend inscribed under the arm of King, reading De[va]varmana (not with absolute degree of certainty).

Rev: A Standing feminine deity-figure with eight-arms, two in front, three on both sides, holding a miniature child-like figure with both hands, head of the child-figure in right-field, head that of an Elephant, with the trunk rolled around the left-breast of the Goddess. Illegible legends on side-margins.

The unique and unseconded nature of this coinage has several layers of significance, which we intend to unravel in the next few paragraphs. The points that call for attention are the following-

Gupta idiom- The coin-type closely follows the Gupta idiom, in which each issuing monarch was shown with bow and arrow, a conceptual exhibition of the military valour and vigor of the King. Through this, the ruler attested his position as the best possessor of all martial skills necessary for governance, and thereby righteously bestowed with divine favor and grace (Altekar, 1957: 10; Kumar, 2017: 78). Till Skandagupta, the Archer-type coins formed a crucial constituent of coinage production of royal Gupta mints. But, in the post-Skandagupta phase, barring Prakāśāditya, only this coin-type was issued by all Imperial Gupta Kings, ranging from Buddha-gupta (c. 475-498 CE) to Viṣṇu-gupta (c. 543-550 CE). This shows that this particular style of presenting imperial sovereign had become immobilized, or was adhered to by all successor states to present themselves in legitimate continuity to the *classical* Gupta Age.

Vangāla niche- Coins issued in post-Gupta Bengal possess certain iconological motifs that place them in a select and specific geo-political orbit. Within the fragmented geo-political situation in Bengal, the pace of state formation was not the same in every territorial division, and occurred most swiftly in Division C (between Bhagirathi and Meghnā rivers, *cf.* Mukherjee, 1992: 5-8), comprising regional polities of Varendra and Vangāla. Past political formations and concentration of capital power allowed this region to unleash imperialist tendencies first, and swayed vast swathes of Bengal. Kingship herein thence firstly attempted to move away from Gupta idiom. While a complete severance was both impractical (*vide supra.*) and unfeasible, innovations could have surely met the objective with finesse. The *Pūrṇa Kumbha* motif, which occurs on all Bengal coins after the inaugural induction by Samāchāradeva, was part and parcel of this schematic only.

Bull standard- The Bull standard had entered Bengal coinage from the time of King Samāchāradeva, who firstly issued coins with much innovation (*Class II:* King with two queens on obverse), though his innovative stance did not last long, as the Archer-type again became predominant from the time of Jayanāga (c. 570-590 CE), who was probably the immediate predecessor of Śaśāṃka. The Bull standard received vigorous impetus during the reign of

Śaśāṃka, who made it his official symbol, and used it actively in his seals (Rohtasgarh clay-matrix) and coins (both Class I and II). The Bull standard affirmed the staunch Śaivite inclination of Śaśāṃka, and further acted favorably in matters of international trade and commerce, especially with South East Asian kingdoms with strong Śaivite bent in royal policy-making (Dalrymple, 2024: 326). This standard could also be taken as a herald of dominant positional status of Śaivism in the sectarian affiliation of the issuing authority.

Samataṭa effect- While performing metallurgical mensuration at Indian Museum, Calcutta, Mukherjee and Lee (1988: 40) noted a peculiar fact- coins with provenance close to our in the ancient coastal area of Samataṭa had relatively more noble metal in the total composition, i.e. they were less adulterated/debased, It was possibly the effect of international trade and with it, the nourishment of an element of trust in Coinage that kept gold-content of Samataṭa mints relatively high. Moreover, trans-national interaction and transactions could have also brought more gold bullion into Samataṭa market. It must also not be ignored that inner areas of Bengal never dealt directly with foreign clients, and relied more or less on an eclectic admixture of barter-exchange and coined currency-system. For these interior lands, Bengal kings mostly minted either copper coins, or for medium to slightly high-value transaction, debased gold coins, a differential practice of numismatic policy-making that finds repeated occurrence throughout different epochs of history (Grierson, 1975: 32).

With the aforementioned facts at our disposal, it is now high time to offer conjectural, hypothetical reconstructions of the particularly mysterious and unparalleled reverse which occupies our prime objective. At this juncture, only two hypotheses seem most probable-

Harvest rites- Given the strong and distinct linkages of both Durgā and Gaṇeśa with harvest activities (especially in Bengal), it is possible that the reverse figuration was an attempt by royal authorities in Bengal to offer propitiation to the two divinities during harvest season. The seasonal-attribution of deity-figures on coins has been a recurrent feature in numismatic annals, straight

from the spring-associated depiction of Nanā on gold-coins of Kaṇiṣka I issued for Indian territories. The most important seasonal festival in Bengal has been Navarātri, where the goddess is worshipped for wealth and prosperity, along with her children, especially Gaṇeśa (Brown, 1991: 22), as recorded in literature since c. 8th Century CE (*see* Sarkar, 2012: 330-342).

Rites and roles- It is known that from an mytho-cultural perspective, Early Medieval Period saw numerous experimentations and innovations, before cults began to get crystallized and assume a shape that resembles their contemporary versions. Samāchāradeva had most probably started a cult of Sarasvati worship, a deity-figure to whom he devoted reverse of his Class II reverse (Mukherjee, 1993: 14). It is possible that Deva-varmana, the primary authority (possibly a ruler from Kāmarūpa) behind issuing this coin, had initiated the reverence of a new, synthetic cultic practice that integrated Gaṇeśa and Durgā with along with their worshippers with each other. While this reverse remained long in circulation, issued by different kings, the quantum of coins issued solely by Deva-varmana far exceeds others (Mukherjee, 1993: 27), while each specific issue also maintained a high metallurgical standard. This shows that the coin was an event-based issuance, one that was closely related to Imperial ambitions.

Royal icons- The figurative aspects of coinage are integrally linked with royal emblems, standards and icons (*cf.* Garuḍa on Gupta coins). When Śaśāṃka made recumbent bull his royal emblem, he not only issued seals with the same standard, but also engraved it on his coins. It is possible that Deva-varmana attempted to make Gaṇeśa-janani Durgā motif his new royal icon. As Mukherjee (1993: 26) speculated, Deva-varmana was stationed as a Governor in Bengal. After demise of Bhāskara-Varmana, Kāmarūpa came under the Mleccha dynasty (Lahiri, 1991: 31). It can be suggested in this light that there is possibility that Deva-varmana was left isolated or stranded in Samatāṭa politics, where he attempted to establish a new kingdom. Folk culture, popularity of specific deities, proximity between particular divinities and diaspora, along with personal predilections often guided the selection process.

Temples and deities- In a recent article, Singh (2021: 13) suggested that divine figures on coins were sometimes also connected with a temple or cult prevalent in order around the place of issuance. In our case, it is possible that for a numismatic innovation, Deva-varmana and his celators chose a Temple-based depiction that was fairly and commonly known in Samatāṭa. The Gaṇeśa-janani Durgā motif has existed since long, in one form or another. The Godhikāvāhinī Durgā shares a similar iconographical slate with the former. Bengal Art features a Mahiṣāsura-mardinī form of Durgā which sees her surrounded by Gaṇas, including her sons- Gaṇeśa and Kārttikeya (Mitter, 2001: 168).

Fig. 06: Godhikāvāhinī Durgā/Gaurī holding Gaṇeśa in Upper Left arm, Pala Period
(*Courtesy-* The Metropolitan Museum, Reg. No. 2015, 519. *Credit-* The Miriam and Ira D.

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Conclusion

In the final analysis, it can be said that within the encompassing mytho-cultural orbit of Śaivism, Gaṇeśa and Durgā share a close contact, by virtue of both of them being connected with harvest rituals, a phenomenon that continues upto this day, and essentially forms a living history, especially in Bengal. However, while it received stimulus during Early Medieval Period, it surely has some strong roots in hoary antiquity.

Although numismatic attestations of Gaṇeśa and Durgā are less when compared to those of Śiva (Nain, 2023: 77), they are nevertheless vital for understanding the development and

formation of the wider and variegated Śaivite worldview, and subsequently Hinduism as a whole. Durgā makes a formal numismatic appearance in Gupta Coinage, which is probably (though, not certainly) linked with their (possible) homeland in Bengal (Mukherjee, 1992: 12). But, what could be said with definiteness is that the figuration of Durgā strongly resembles Nanā on Kuṣāṇa coins (Ghose, 2006: 88; Srinivasan, 2005: 134). The same however, could not be said for Gaṇeśa, whose presence can be gauged only from a solitary terracotta seal, that could be a temple seal (Thaplyal, 1972: xi), issued by the renowned Jāgīśvara temple in present-day Uttarakhand, whose earliest structures exhibit Gupta influence (Gupta and Vijayakumar, 2011: 62).

With gradual pace of time, the figure of the Goddess Durgā on this coin undergoes progressive corruption, while the image of Gaṇeśa is distorted beyond conception. Mukherjee (1992: 27) speculated that Deva-Varmana referred herein may in sooth, stand for a possible successor of Bhāskara-Varmana, the known last monarch of the Varmana House of Kāmarūpa (Barua 1951: 60). What is more revealing, however, is the conception of Gaṇeśa as an elephant babe, a not usual form of Gaṇeśa. Numerous Medieval texts in Bengal portray an intimately enmeshed domestic relationship between Durgā and Gaṇeśa (Majumdar, 2021: 143-149). It is possible that the die-artist in Samatāta received inspiration from Gupta sculptures, to which they contributed their own meritorious artistic genius by making the reverse scenario comply better with the Mother-Goddess motif of their chief source of earnest propitiation- Durgā. Although no textual or iconographical conventions exist to illustrate the normative idea to be represented, scholars generally refer to the statuary depicting eight/four-armed Durgā with Gaṇeśa in arm/lap as Gaṇeśa-Janani Durgā, an art-motif with innumerable reiteration throughout the temples of Bengal (Goyal, 1984: 78).

With this information in possession, it can be well asserted that this numismatic design possibly serves as a precursor to the renowned and traditionally reiterated art-motif, especially in a Śākta context. This emergent trend possibly garnered further succor and support from the gradual

domestication of Durgā, followed by the induction of Gaṇeśa in rituals performed during harvest season (Sircar, 2004). However, this could have led to some interesting scenarios, as indicated by the limited provenance of these issues (1972 *Indian Archaeology Review*). Samatāṭa, as a coastal trade centre, was closely intertwined with other overseas ports of commerce, which obviously made cultural constructs and contexts mobile. Śiva could serve as a strong linking anchorage, due to the shared reverence of the deity in transnational cultures. The same, however, cannot be averred for the present art-motif, due to the limited cognizance and its innovative nature. Ultimately, it can only be said, with definitive uncertainty, that the coins were issued for either commemorative purposes (ex. A festival, ritual etc.), or was a copious issue (the die-artist possibly copied the motif from a live sculpture). Future discoveries and researches would surely unveil novel data that would further enlighten our understanding of the past and its people.

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